

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF HEADTEACHER'S AND DEPUTY HEADTEACHERS CONFLICT DEVELOPMENT ON TEAM WORK IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOL IN KENYA

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Abstract:

The research study critically analyzed the impact of head teacher's and deputy head teacher's conflict development on team works in public primary school in Kenya. The study sought to establish the root causes of conflicts among the head teachers and deputy head teachers, perceptions of the stakeholders on the head teacher's and deputy head teachers, impact of the conflict resolution measures between the head teacher's and deputy head teachers on team work in public primary school in Kenya. Leadership challenges leading to chronic conflicts that has persisted in public primary schools and in high rise according to ministry of education report. Always conflicts occur whenever disagreement exists in a social setup between individuals or group and negotiations has become a song in the public schools in Kenya. The researchers sought to justify that in dead there exist a great disagreement between head teacher's and deputy head teacher's an issue that must be urgently addressed and if not taken serious might adversely effect on team work at work places. Also, the research sought to justify that conflicts leads to social desertification. Demoralization, stress, unhappiness, frustration and a sense of low self-esteem this is a thriving factor to disunity and weakens the bond of team work in an organization. The study defined the team head teacher, deputy head teacher's highlighting their major roles in a learning institution and to the community and to all education stakeholders. The study was based on team work theory so called Bruce tuck man theory of 1965 enriched by START TEAM MODEL. This theory had

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four main stages titled forming, storming, norming and performing. The head teacher's do not only recognize the fact that they formed a group with their deputies. The time they were put together so they must focus on their individual strengths since there was need to bring out goals of the school they lead in order to make a difference in academic arena. The head teacher's and deputy head teacher's required a strong bond between them and other staff and insubordinate staffs to facilitate happiness that was necessary for team work at work place. The researchers used content reviews and desk analysis function design. The design was preferred since it facilitated more critical analysis than the statistically qualitative methods used in the same qualitative studies. The study found major causes of conflict development between head teacher's and deputy head teachers to be inadequate information, different personalities/ value and characters, experience/ qualifications s, access to superiors, limited resources, role conflicts, poor work conditions, administration styles used by leaders, favoritism, tribalism and nepotism practiced by leaders. Most deputies unlike head teachers had no operational space called offices and whenever the head teachers was absent, the offices remained locked and keyed. Findings also found that most head teacher never trusted their deputies with the resources, finances and personnel an issue that cannot facilitate team work in a working place. The findings of the study was that all stake holders perceptions in the persistence conflict development between the head teachers and deputy head teachers was that it diversely affect team work, academic performance, social relationship and reputation and ought to be done away with completely. The study recommended that the school heads and their deputy head teachers to be trained on conflict prevention measures, management strategies and resolution skills in order to prevent, manage and resolve them in amicable way to facilitate team work at work places. The researchers further recommended the introduction of teaching of controversial issues at teacher colleges and in universities for both undergraduates and postgraduates pursuing educational causes in order to bring up teachers who are well conversant on how to live with controversy. The researchers also recommended the establishment of resolution committee of qualified, experienced personals at school level; help improve the working relationship between head teachers and deputy head teachers to reduce the rising rate of conflict development in public primary schools in Kenya.

Keywords: impact, head teachers, deputy head teachers, conflicts development, public schools

1. Introduction

School is a system. It has several parts put together in order to achieve its goals. Just like body parts, each organ has to function in order to realize its set targets for consistency, orderliness and smooth running of a school there must be hierarchy put in place. Every individual is important in playing supportive role smooth and effective running of the school that is why teacher's service commission has assigned every public primary school a school head teacher and a deputy. Head teachers and deputy head teachers have to work together in order to realize a school target. In Kenya education system today at primary level have of late registered a lot of conflicts leading to stand still of school operations, and disunity of the staff subordinate staffs and the community at large, (Republic of Kenya, 2002). The report from the ministry of education reflects that the fact that the education system is managed by government policies and things seems to be right, public education institutions have persistently recorded an increase in cases of conflicts. The resent past it is a conflict between head teachers and the deputy head teachers. Omboko (2010) indicated that conflicts in schools reduce the strength and resources such as social support and interaction among teachers and other stake holders. It increase problems in schools set up and weakens the team work. According to new storm and David, (2002), unresolved interpersonal conflicts lead to fall out in co-operation and team work at individuals' level. Some may give up feel unwanted, while others may develop negative attitudes and let go while others may be stressed, depressed and worked up.

Kipyego B, (2009) argued that a large number of schools in Kenya have been rocked by the wave of conflicts and this majority affects public schools. According to Kama j, (2002) the genesis of the said conflict is the disunity created between the head teachers and deputy head teachers. The Government of Kenya through the ministry of education and teachers service commission has stipulated guidelines on role of head teachers and deputy head teachers in a school. Deputy Head teachers are authorized to deputize the head teachers in their absence. Most research findings found that there is no harmonies co-relationship between the head teachers and their deputy head teachers. The head teachers in most of the cases regard their deputy as threats but not friends. Most head teachers' moles, frustrate, embarrass and torment their deputies. They are given no room to participate in administrative decisions, some has no space called office to work on or they can be allocated any small room in the name of an office. They are the store keepers but sometimes they can be denied even the key to the stores and given to senior or any other favorite teacher in the school. According to Kama J., (2002) the teachers service commission should move with speed to improve on the welfare of the deputy head teachers office in order to eliminate the development of conflict between the head teachers and deputy head teachers in the school setting so as

to safeguard on team work. Always where there is human being, and interaction is guarantee there is always possibility of agreement and disagreement. In Kenyan public primary schools the persisting conflict that is being experienced has not started now. It has its ways back as old as the origin of man. Biblically Adam and Eve were sent out of Garden of Eden because there existed conflict between them and God. (Genesis: 3:1-20) and also Satan called Lucifer was sent from Heaven to Earth because there was conflict; between it and God. The world war was fought because there was conflict between the super power countries and the emerging super power by then. Many countries had their reign overthrown because of conflict and many countries up-to-date have no political Government in place because of conflicts so the early revolution, industrializations economic and technological innovations has to face conflict challenges before they carry out the day. This may arise due to incompatibility disagreements between and among individuals and groups over different divergence opinions, resources, ideas and ideologies, benefits, emotions which results to bitterness and opposition (Kipyago 2013), Laue (1990); in Johdi & Apitree (2012) and Tschannen M., (2001) in Shamohammadi (2014); many kingdoms and sovereign countries have been brought down due to unresolved conflicts most of the giant academic schools have since been declared academic failures, due to their sudden collapse due to administrative conflicts between the head teachers and the deputy head teachers.

Some deputies or head teachers have gone for the grave cursing either their leads or their deputies to be behind the course of their death. Some head teachers have resigned or have found their schools ungovernable reciting the conflict between them and their deputies as the cause of their administration challenges. Tshuma R, Ndloru S, and Bhebhe S, (2016) cited in their research study that when conflict occurs there is tendency for morale to be lowered therefore it results to a stressful, unhappiness situation thus adversely affect team work at working station. The head teachers must accept the fact that deputy head teachers are the rightful successors to their positions as head teachers and stop viewing them as a threat or a timing bomb that is waiting to explode on them at any time. Conflicts can be avoided through according to some researchers it is part and parcel of life, Opuku A.; Takyiz and Owusu M.; (2015). Suggested that conflict in life is an avoidable and constitute part of every day's life Makaye J.; and Amosa P.; (2012), in their study supported the idea as argued that negotiation has become the chorus of the nation in every household and negotiation is brought by conflicts. Tshabalala (2013), Opuku A.; Takyil & Owusu M.; (2015) and Dick & Thodlana (2013) cited that conflict is a fact of life and cannot be avoided at all stages of human life is a common matter in an organization and work places and if managed well it can be constructive and if otherwise it can be harmful and can create unhealthy differences in the work place and switch off the attentions of stakeholders from the institutional goals to the conflict itself and the people involved.

In the school environment, conflict is uncalled for. It weakens team work and adversely affects harmony, unity and the smooth running of the institutions. It further destructs the goals of the team and leads them to poor performance, demoralization, truancy and much more unprofessional conducts. The public primary school in Kenya are right in the middle of this crisis with religious leaders becoming more religious to provoke the super natural power to interview and protect them against the conflict odds. On the other hand the superstitions leaders depending on the power of their gods and ancestors to safeguard them against the odds of the conflicts at their places of work. If this issues are not urgently the team work, a powerful tool to connect a group of people to be one the same vision & mission for ultimate goal will no longer prevail at all. To the best, interest of public primary schools all those who have been privileged to be the head teachers should know how to lead their teams at different stages of their reign. They must recognize the success of their deputies as well as other individuals. They should accept to treat their deputies with the respects they deserve. As much as the head teacher are the senior teachers service commission argents at school and are responsible for managing staff and setting policies for the school they should embrace their deputies and co-work together. Together with their deputies, head teachers should work on the policies to motivate but not demobilize teachers. The two should lead the teaching fraternity as a team but not everybody with their squad timing each other to teach one another apart. It is the role of both the head teachers and the deputy head teachers to evaluate the performance and set goals and institutional expectations together. The head teachers should know to themselves that is there is conflict between them and their deputies them there won't be recruitment and retention of good tutors in a school. As school spokespersons, they should always react from the same scripts in order to know what to tell their subordinate staffs, students, teachers and community at large. Portaged with these circumstances, the present study based on the formational problems, the researchers critically analyzed the impact of the head teachers and deputy head teachers' conflicts development on team work in public primary schools in Kenya.

2. Statement of the Problem

A Learning institution must have a leader to head the institution. The head is called the head teacher deputized by a deputy head teachers. Head teachers are the senior teachers at school and are responsible for managing personnel's resources & setting school policies at school level, the head teachers is the senior teachers service commissioner's argent entrusted to manage thus to direct, control, command and supervise all the resources and curriculum implementation in the school. Head teachers are appointed by teacher's service commission and are empowered to carry their

diligence duties without fear of favor. Teacher's service commission is a statutory independent body that was formed by parliament act in 1967 to manage teachers. According to teacher's service commission employment act the head teachers with the help of their deputies are authorized to be the top most managers in a public learning institution. They are required to perform the roles of managers at all levels. They should motivate and lead their teaching staffs, evaluate the school performance and set dreams and targets. They are expected be mission and vision providers to their institutions. They are supposed to prudently expect to be the chief accountants to manage the school finances effectively. Head teachers are entrusted to give good leadership, be vision carriers God provide all the necessary resources that are required in a school to facilitate effective & interactive curriculum and co-curricular implementation in their schools.

The post of a deputy head teachers is not an inherited post neither it is also a reorganized post that one holds only after an appointment by the employer or their senior argents in an acting capacity. The core duties of the deputy head teachers is to deputies the head teachers to provide professional leadership and management for all staff in order to get high quality care and to secure high quality curriculum and co-curricular delivery. The deputy head teachers assist the head teachers to oversee the prudent use of resources and improved standard of learning and achievement for all students. Both of them are teacher's service commission employees of which each one of them has their roles defined as per their letter of appointment guided by teachers service commission employment act. Their use is also guided by constitution of Kenya (2010) and employer and employee relationship labours law act 2007. The teachers service commission, the employer do expect the due to co-work together to facilitate team work in their work place in order to realize the set target of their schools. However in most cases as teachers service constantly keeps on having conflict with their employees teachers leading to strikes year in year out, the head teachers and their deputies are as well in constant conflict leading to stand still of school operations and disunity at school level. In most cases as observed, the head teacher and their deputies in public primary schools in Kenya do not work together due to several reasons. Republic of Kenya (2001) indicates that conflicts in Kenyan schools have become a thorn on the flesh and therefore all the stakeholders in education sectors should take a great concern. The study further argued that if these conflicts are allowed to continue, it will not only ruin education team work at work places but also destructively destroy education sector, community and the national development of the whole country Okumbe (2008) reasoned that managing personal, there is a need for the head teachers to attract human resources. So it is important to motivate and retain the human resources. However if there is conflict existing between the head teachers and their deputies, it is impossible to recruit and retain good personal resources in a school. The school is as good as the head teacher. A good head teacher motivates himself and

motivates others. Head teachers should not lack motivation for themselves and should not demotivate their deputies as well as their teaching staff. Good head teachers should assist their deputies to gain the necessary leadership skills, knowledge and right attitude for effective delivery in their anticipated leadership role. The head teachers should facilitate their deputies to attend conflict resolutions courses (Okumbe 2008)

Conflict interferes with team work. People who work as a team may not only have the same goals to achieve but they have mutual trust. The issue that must be urgently addressed by teachers service commission (TSC) the employees of which is not addressed the country education is at risk is leadership conflict between the head teachers and their staff and subordinate staff usually get affected or infected directly or indirectly in such conflicts whenever they occur. The study has been done to prove that these unnecessary conflicts are eroding team work in our learning institutions. And has adverse effect to personal management and academic goals of the learning institutions. Some to which leads to everlasting enmity and loss of life of teachers involved in such wrangles. The gap in knowledge has therefore necessitated the proposed study.

4. Purpose of the Study

The study was to critically analysis the impact of the head teacher's and their deputy head teacher's conflict development on team work in public primary schools in Kenya.

5. Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Critically analyses the impact and cause if conflict among head teachers and their deputies on team work in public primary school in Kenya.
2. To critically analyses the impact of the stakeholders' perception on head teachers and their deputies' conflict development on team work in public primary school in Kenya.
3. To critically analyses the impact of the conflict resolution measures between head teachers and their deputies on team work in public primary schools in Kenya.

6. Research Questions

1. What are the impact and causes of conflict development amongst head teachers and their deputies on team work in public primary schools in Kenya?

2. What are the impact of the stakeholder's perception on head teacher and their deputies' conflict development on team work in public primary schools in Kenya?
3. What are the impact of the conflict resolution measures between head teachers and their deputy head teachers and public primary schools in Kenya?

7. Research Methodology

The researchers made their research based on study that used content and desk analysis design. The study was based on thus method since it allows room for constructive critical analysis better than the quantization statistics result when used in similar research. The researchers argue their critique as positive evaluation of impact of head teachers and their deputies head teachers. The researchers justify that if this conflict is not resolved, managed and prevented; it is the surest way of ditching the country's education into chaos, starting by killing the team work at every work station. This issue that cannot be ignored for it has multiple complications in educational sector in the whole nation.

8. Significance of the Study

Every nation is it developed or developing invests heavily in their country's education. This has got a lot to do with development in the future and the future hope of the generation to come. Education is not only the key to success but also the engine of which other sectors like health, agriculture, industrialization, fishery and many others depend on. Since it is an employer policy that every learning institution must be headed by a school head teacher and deputized by a school deputy head teacher who should team up to work together without any conflict and that is not what is happening 100%, then therefore the findings of this research may help the employer (teachers service commission) to put in place effective qualified and experienced conflict resolution school to national level and supervise their more. The findings may help the employer to ensure there is a policy to ensure all current serving head teachers and deputy head teachers are equipped with necessary conflict prevention, management and resolution skills. The ministry of education may use the findings of the study to formulate educational policy that facilitate the learning of controversial issues, conflict management skill and dispute resolutions at teacher training colleges, university graduate pursuing focally of education and all serving teachers in order to produce leaders who know how to handle controversial matters, live with happiness and resolve disputes whenever they may arise.

9. Theoretical Frame Work

The study was based on team work theory so called Bruce Tuckman theory enriched by START Team Model. The theory created in 1965 has four main stages titled forming, storming, norming and performing. When the head teacher is given a deputy to deputies, he has been given a team mate to form a team. The head teacher must know their deputies at every stage. This theory explains that effective team work in work place depends on when individuals as they use and develop their strengths. At every stage, the head teacher must recognize the fact that, he/she and their deputies are a fully formed group meant to work together and deliver towards their school goals. At every stage, the head teachers as senior to their deputies should induct their deputy head teachers as they grow through these clearly defined stages. The head teacher should know how to develop the team work first with his/her deputy before they develop team work with the rest of the teaching staff, non-teaching staff students and the community.

The head teachers should view the deputies as a supporter and emphasize on mutual relationship and trust in order to work as a team. The head teachers should win the trust of their deputies, know what they require to deputies them and put in place the necessary facilities and resources to make the work of their deputies easy at every stage. This theory requires the head teachers and their deputies to focus on individuals' strength particularly when in the aim to bring out the school goals that are needed to make a difference. The theory requires align the strengths of individuals with effective team work and focus on meaningful outcome also considering the phases and the environment within the team are situated.

10. A critical analysis of the impact of head teachers and deputy head teachers conflicts development on team work in public primary school in Kenya.

10.1 Critical Definition of Conflict

Where people lives there must be disagreement of ideas, ideologies born out of social differences, cultural and religious dogmas and educational differences among other issues. Opoka, Asare, Jakyil & Owusu M. (2016) define conflict as discord that emerges in a social setting because of matters of importance or whenever emotional antagonism results into contrast. It can arise when individuals or group beliefs or interest of one member of the group is either denied by or unaccepted to one or more members of another group. Kipyego (2013) support the claims of Laue, (1990). In Johdi & Apitree (2012), and Tshamen-moran 2001 in Shahrmoa Mnadi, 2014) in that conflict has the resisting ideas and actions of different parties catalyzed by the opposition of one group or individual to another group or individuals in attempt to meet goals different from that of the other individuals or groups leading to antagonistic state. Conflict can be defined as a rational disagreement or incomparability dissatisfaction between or among

two or more persons over clashing goals, resources, ideologies, noshes, benefits, opinions, and emotion and feelings which lead to bitterness and opposition. According to Nyamajiwe (2000, p3), Conflict is the opposition of individuals or group, interest, idea or purpose. It can be between two people or more groups or different parties, nations or continents.

Furthermore, K. (1990) echoed the idea that conflict is an outcome of struggle between two or more completing positions held by one or more persons usually that emerges from incompatible beliefs, ideologies or goals. Conflict emerges whenever perceives or ideal interest antagonized. According to Hanson (1991), in any organization be it a school or a profit making organization conflict is unavoidable either positively or retroactively.

11. Types of Conflicts

According to Hanson, (1991), there are several categories of conflict namely intra role, inter-role, intra-department intra-organizational, inter personal and interpersonal conflicts. The most commonly faced conflict like the one in question is interpersonal conflict. It entails the quality of interactions between two or more teachers. Hanson (1991) argues that this conflict developed when two members in a group (like the head teacher and the deputy head teacher in a group of teachers in the school) normally amicable friends usually find themselves eying the same promotion to a single job. In conclusion, lack of acceptance leads to conflict and resistance behavior according to Stewont, J. and Dangelo, G. (1980). There are three types of conflicts thus conflict over image much concerned with identity of who issues such as who is more knowledgeable, who has more power (authority), who has mandate to carry out a certain duty or obligation and who has what personality traits or behaviors? The second is role conflict mostly results from contradicting interpretation of what is that is discrepancies on the duties we carry out. The third conflict is the conflict over basic values results over image perceptions or content i.e. difference in cultural beliefs, ideas religious dogmas in this context all the above conflict affect the co-existence head teachers and deputy head teachers of which return adversely affect the team work at their work stations.

12. Causes of conflict development between head teachers and deputy head teachers and their impacts on team work in primary schools in Kenya

12.1 Head's Leadership Style

A leader is a person who faces charge and directs the group's performance in this case the head teacher is the leader and teaching staff and the deputy are the followers. Whatever decision, behavior and action a leader do directly affect the followers head

teacher thus is the legitimate head or appointed head of learning institution for example headmaster or head mistress. Most head teachers at the present are majority who were born during Kenyatta's era and brought up during the former president of Kenya Daniel T. Arap Moi when Democracy was given minimal space to thrive and autocratic was the order of the day. They prefer autocratic leadership unlike their deputies who cherishes charismatic, democratic and transformational leadership. According to Dick Thodlana (2013), their study revealed that most of the school management practices were associated by dictatorial syndrome complimented by top-down order of command with strategic administrative authority from highest level of hierarchy enforced with brutal consequences for any form of disobedience. Quite often, this is the most source of conflict between the head teachers and their deputies. It causes tension between the school head teachers and deputies and the rest of the teaching staff. The head teachers who are viewed as autocratic and bureaucratic leaders practices the extreme form of transactional leadership. They exert high level of power over their followers or team members. Their deputies and teaching staffs are given few opportunities for making suggestion. Most of people resent being treated like this. Quite often the people being treated like this collude to form a resisting group that is why in those institutions the minority considered sycophant will follow the head teachers while the minority considered "freedom fighters" or "transformists", "savant leaders" or democrats will follow the deputies to advocate for leadership style of a true leader, who inspire has or her team with a shared vision of the future.

Most deputies are found in the staff rooms, they are highly visible and spent a lot of time communicating to the teaching staff. They don't lead from the front; they tend to delicate duties amongst their team. They are enthusiastic charismatic. The sharp difference between these charismatic young energetic deputies and the old grad autocratic head teacher's leaders to conflict over image, role conflict and basic value conflicts. The young charismatic leader if it the head teacher or the deputy may believe more in him/herself than in their team of the immediate supervisor or deputy usually leading to the collapsing of team work.

The structural factors put in place by autocratic, bureaucratic leaders in an organization usually put people off from associating with them because if this autocratic leadership usually leads to high level of truancy and chronic absenteeism. It also leads to the death of team work since team work output is not reorganized. Atal Johdi & A. Pitree, (2012). Argued that most school heads have tension with their teachers because most persons do not like being informed what to do as in the case of autocratic school leaders who if they are told what to do by their transformation charismatic deputy head teachers they take personal and pick up a quarrel hence resulting into persistence conflict and finally the school split into two groups not to deliver towards the school goals but to focus on the conflict itself.

12.2 Experience and Qualification

In service, there are long serving teachers who have gathered accumulative several years of experience. In a school there is always a mix up of the newly employed, the more experience old guards. When an old guard experienced teachers holds the position of being a lead teacher and is give a deputy who is young and has not taken many years in service, the young teachers may perceive the elderly head teacher as old fashioned who knows no modern skills of leadership. The old guard may also despise the young deputy as inexperienced young person who cannot command respect and knows very little in the teaching profession Pukkapan (1999 in Shahmoharumadi, 2014). The young tutor and the old guard may have two different perceptions on leadership this perception will result to conflict when the two individuals are not willing to work as a team. The young task may prefer they put in place a simple management structure while the old guard being the immediate boss may advocate for professional bureaucracy and adhocracy management structure. If may image that the old guard as a leader is I don't care professional who bank on his/her years of experience in service and age, can utter anything thoughtlessly or slash out at a team member anyhow, the young man in second in command may be acting opposite the conflict that will emerge between the two will reduce the morale of the team work, increase absenteeism and division of the staff to avoid conflict and safeguard the team work at the work place often the best leaders burry down their differences cherish transformational leadership, hold integrity of everyone, set clear goals communicate well with your Juniors to build up team work and inspire them by sharing your visions & missions.

12.3 Indiscipline / Unethical Behavior

Teaching requires discipline from all the stakeholders. Teachers who found themselves in teaching professions as the last option not because it was their choice, mostly live in denial. Kipyego (2013) state that those teachers only teachers to earn a living in their professions as a tutor and they ever complain, murmur, grumble and even fight whoever stand on that their way to make them have work done. In case any is the deputy, they will always blame the head teacher who will always delegate duty to them. If it be the case, they are the head teachers they may cling on tools of making the work of their deputies so miserable and difficult. In Kenya due to lack of job, people join teaching profession simply because they have no otherwise. Upon promotion, if booth the deputy and head teachers belong to those groups they may work together. If otherwise, there must emerge sharp contradiction verging from commitment, altitude, dedication and professionalism.

Kipyego (2013) further suggest that if he head teacher is uncommitted and always an absentee, latecomer, dishonest inaccessible and autocratic, it become ineffective to enforce discipline to their own teaching staff and even their immediate

deputies. Also the researcher argues that whoever challenges this barbaric unprofessional behaviors has to face the conceive power in him/her either verbal or written threats. This has always been the cause of conflict among the head teachers and their deputies and it diversely affect team work in the work.

12.4 Superiority Complex

Head teachers are the senior most teachers' service commission argent in the school. With the arrival of contracting appraisal in the teachers line of duty. They behave like demy gods. Once appointed ahead teacher, you enjoy some privileges. In the current status they recommend you for promotion or deny you that privilege. They have influential & conceived power. They can quote the teachers service commission code of conduct, code of ethics, TSC act 2015, children's act 2001 and many other off head page after page. They are privileged to be the finance accountants collecting both legal and "illegal" funds in the school. They can afford to drive new brand cars and build rental houses within the shortest time possible. According to walker in kipyego (2013) some school heads forget themselves and is carried up by their status that comes with their position that they feel they are inseparable from office.

They value nobody not even their deputy head teachers. They have a common usual say that goes as "it is my time" Randall B. Dunham and Joh P. (1989), argued that essentially everything affects everything else. That means negative actions feedback to negatively affect further performance and vase versa. The head teacher who have reached the print of being carried away by the status position do not give feedback to help to improve the outcome or to maintain the team work they are insensitive they can diminish performance reduce miracle and hurl abuse to any team member. They expect their deputies to be honest, ethical and submissive yet they are arrogant, proud and bully. Their actions are unchallengeable, whoever dare challenge their authority and an action has to meet the wrath of their aggression and ideal threats.

12.5 Management of Funds

Head teachers are the chief accountants in the public primary schools. They are entrusted with public funds in the school accounts. Some head teachers are not transparent to indicate how the school funds have been utilized. They lack and key the documents pertaining school funds and school development. Others authorized the collection of funds that are "illegal" in the name of development funds, activity fee, admission fee, special program fee, educational four or school trips without presenting the budget of how the money will be used or has been used sometimes deputies may be required to facilitate the collection of such funds failure of which it will be treated as sabotage, insubordination, negligence of duty and many other relevant terms. Finally warning letter, threats and "a show course why letter". Madziyire et al (2010) argued

that in some schools the management might have interest to save the money in their account may be to generate interest while the sometime demanding for excellent performance. In such instance, teachers will request for funds to allocate for the buying of instructional materials. If the deputy forwards such request to the head teachers, they may be viewed as inciters who incite the teachers against the administration resulting to conflict development. If the money is not granted immediately teachers may withdraw their effort academic results. If the money is not avails, the parents will rise against the administration and seek for the transfer of the head teacher. The student may go on strike demanding for better quality services. It will be seen as the deputy head teacher is working on the down fall of the head teacher in order to get promoted. Thus results to conflict.

12.6 Personal Factors

These include level of skills and abilities, different personalities, favoritisms, nepotism and feeling in secured at work by leadership. Every individual is unique. The personal factors relate to the degree of difference between group members (Johdi & Apitee, 2012). Due to personality factors people cannot do things the same. Ndhiovu 2006). Rahim in Johdi & Apritree (2012) agreed that different personalities are ideal factors that must exist in any group set up so the school set up is not excluded and thus why there must be a co-worker at work place with is difficult to get along with. According to G&A. partners (2010) identified the personalities such as bulldozers, the exploders, the complainers, the wet blanket, the know it all, the abrasive person and the staler. The bulldozers are abusive in nature whole the exploders can easily burst in emotions and are filled with rage. The wet blanket are usually pessimistic always believe nothing can work as long as there has been a conflict. The "know it all" they term themselves experts in everything. The abrasive person is a hardworking and a goal oriented but critical and insensitive to other people's feelings. The stallers are the habitually indecisive. Due to these different personalities some people would not want to tolerate others some deputies may not want the personalities their head teachers have and vise vasa resulting to conflict. Broni (2013) states that due to personalities some teachers just do not like the bitter truth that some people are their administrators. Some tutors with stronger personalities feel more competent than their administrators and therefore undermines them and will never co-operate with them. Some deputies with stronger personalities will literally fail to respect the rank of their head teachers if they have week personalities. They trust they are more capable and more so if they have higher qualifications that the serving school head teachers. This finally divides the teaching staff into different groups hence weakening the spirit of the team work.

12.7 Favoritism / Nepotism / Tribalism

Favoritism means to prefer someone or group of people from a segment of a team simply because administration likes him/her. Nepotism is the favoring of a relative or personal friend because of their relationship rather than because of their personalities & ability. Tribalism is the condition of showing tribal or identifying with one because of their tribe. The head teachers have got their favorite whom they usually favor despite of the laid down procedures. Thus might be a parent member of teaching staff, subordinate staff or a community member. At times, arise the conflict of interest the privileges that should be given to deputy head teachers are sometimes exchanged along the line of favoritism, nepotism or tribalism. When promotion a rises instead of the head teacher recommending the deputy to be promoted, they recommend their favorite sycophants or a personal friend or a relative or a tribe man to be promoted so do the same with staff. Carver development this results to conflicts in a school setting hence leading to hatreds, unhappiness, bitterness and frustration. Sometimes the qualified personal are left after the rough interview which sometime has been conducted by the deputies and the favorite of the head teachers or a close friend or a tribes men is granted a chance. Tendering may as well follow the same trend due to favoritism nepotism and tribalism the head teachers and deputy head teachers may turn to be great enemies in a school setting finally the whole team will not work together. Omboko in Kepyego (2013) agreed to support this ide by saying that head teachers usually favor other tutors at the expense of others, usually leading discontentment among other teachers. Kepyego (2013) cited that by not treated workers equally, leaders encourage a sense of resentment and disunity that can demotivate workers and damage togetherness and team spirit. Leading to discontentment, resentment, anger, bitterness hatreds and discrimination which finally leads to rumors', jealousy only and antagonist at place of work. If this happen, a deputy who feel discriminated will distrust head teacher and will never be open to have their conflicts resolved. Instead of unity and team work, it divides and generates destructions. Complain, suspiciousness and mistrust.

12.8 Insecure Hardship

Insecure means not comfortable or confident in oneself or uncertain situations. By age must head teachers are advanced in age and are looking forward retiring sooner or soonest from the service. They are sure their deputies who may look twice younger than them are the right successors, readily willing to succeed them. Education wise in most cases where the deputies are younger and more educated, the head feels threatened and insecure with the presence of young deputy. The head teacher may think the young teacher may be promoted any tie to replace them. The head teachers may know they are incompetent and their deputies are competent, they will feel insecure to work with such a deputy whom they may feel is out to expose their

weakness. According to ration with z (2014) insecurity is feeling one is not equal to the task they face they may know though they may put a brave face to cheat others that they can. Such leaders may target the person whom they fear to outdo them and bully the or become arrogant to them or show them power game of intimidation and frustration deputies who sound threat to their head teachers because of their personalities, character traits, qualifications, charismatic and transformational leadership styles usually get mysteries transfer to other schools. They can also be targeted and trapped is set traps leading to in conductive working atmosphere till they languish their post nor seek for their transfer themselves. Sometimes they are denied even the space to work in the name of the office. They are put under watch by instilling spices to tell whatever they are doing in the school and outside the school. They are not allowed to associate freely with other teaching staff, subordinate staff and students and parents. This leads to total discrimination and absence of good for nothing with skills the spirit of team work.

13. Critical analyses of the impact of conflict resolution measures between head teachers and deputies and impact on team work in public primary schools

Conflict resolution measures refer to ways of solving conflicts. Among them being avoidance, non-attention, physical separation, limited interaction, compromises and confrontation (Thakaye J. and Ndofine P, (2012).)

13.1 Physical Separation

This involves moving the conflicting individuals away from each other. The fact is that when people do not interact and groups avoid interaction too there shall be no disagreement therefore conflicts shall be avoided completely. If every time conflicts arises as it always does between the head teacher and deputy head teachers then the solution is to separate them, then for how long will you do that? That means one of them must be transferred to another school probably the deputy. If you transfer the deputy, another one will come and somebody must be promoted to occupy the vacant office. If the conflict arises, again you will separate them. the head teachers should know that if their deputies stand behind them they should protect them and if they stand beside them they should respect them, they should not be separated if they are separated there should be no team work and if there is no team work they shall be defeated to realize the school goals. The head teachers should embrace unity of teamwork and should not agree to be separated on the basic of their differences and conflicts. They should know that alone can stand but together people can "talk walk and win a war". Alone one can enjoy but together people can celebrate. Alone one can

smile but together people can laugh. Achieving school goals through team work leads to victory celebration and joy filled with laughter.

13.2 Limited Interaction

This is when the conflicting parties are allowed to interact on a minimal encounter. If is almost impossible for the boss and the deputy to have limited encounter for they have to reason together, strategies together and plan together always. You don't need to be wisest, smartest and most brilliant such that you can't interact with others be courageous bold and humble to discuss you conflicts. Don't avoid one another. Avoid admitting that conflict exists amongst you such that you should avoid seeing one another. It is the conflict that should be avoided. (Sompa M. 2015). Flippo (2000) argued that total absence of discord in a work place would be unheard of, an impossibility, unimaginable unacceptable and a pointer things are not wright and is a sign of oppression. Bruat (1992) recommends that reaching a positive resolution of conflict should be the ultimate objective. Wheeler's (1995) has the view that teachers who choose to avoid each other do not always get involved in a conflict because it is a way of toleration to escape clashing to each other Connie (2003) suggested that avoiding each other in order to interact millennially may only apply when it is necessary to give some time and space to conflict when the parties involved are not willing to engage in conflict discussion and constructive resolution. Barker (2009) holds the view that avoidance to give limited interaction might not be the best for team work but it can as well solve conflict in an institution. The researcher suggest that conflict may disappear over time if the continuous contact between the conflicting parties are reduced and they realized that what upset about them in the past is just minor issues that are not important any longer.

Thus method do not favor team work hence if used may weaken team spirit in the school setting for it only allow interaction of people who should work as team in seldom only under formal situations like school meetings guided with strict agenda to be followed. Kindler, (1998:42) argued that avoidance or limited interaction is not the best way for reaching a long term solution because the genesis of cause of the conflict is retained

13.3 Confrontation/Integration/Collaborating Powerful-Powerful, Win-Win

If involves mutual difference but conflict is. In most cases can be referred to natural and health conflict. The sources of conflict are identified and tabled for discussion. Hanson, (1996), emphasis is put on the achievement of the common interest of the conflicting individuals or groups. Rahim (1992) callers it as the integration or the "I, win/ you win" response it involves considering both parties under conflict important and the head teachers also consider themselves important. In most cases most of the head teachers

are carried away by the status of their office such that they cannot humble themselves agree their deputies are also important neither do they want to recognize the mediators as vital people appoint that makes thus method almost impossible to the used to resolve dispute and conflict development between head teachers and deputy head teachers in public primary school. Confrontations style can also be called co-operative style. Rahim (1992) states that it requires the expression of feelings, beliefs and ideologies openly and honestly to others (it positive or negative), listening to others and constructively responding to their claims in a well-defined way. This style is hardly used not unless the principle is a humble person and in his/her opinion would want to find out feelings and experiences of the deputy and is sincere in his/her quest to have a long lasting solution to long standing conflict (Irene, 2011)

13.4 Obliging Style

Is where the head teacher put the interest of others and the institution first, decides to ignore their differences, and satisfies others concerns. The head teacher tries to absorb conflict by minimizing differences with the deputy head teacher. (Graft, 2009) claims that it is used when one realizes that relations are more important than issues and inspiration is needed to the junior staff. It involves the use of excuses, being silent, using soft languages being reluctant in speaking and giving in to other party's ideas (Johns, 1988). This method portrays. The head, as a weaker vase, with weak personalities of which majority of head teachers may not accept. In team work everybody must be considered equally important; therefore this strategy is a threat to team work at work place

13.5 Dominating Style

The use of power and total aggressive behavior to control conflicts Namusi, (2012) argued that the effects of using dominating style are always dangerous and destructive. The study further argues that this style accelerate conflict instead of controlling. It diminishes and disrespects the thoughts and the feelings of other people. This is the worst ever weapon to fight team work at the work place for it does not advocate for freedom and democracy can only be used by autocratic, bureaucratic, transactional leaders for they are non transforms and unit-democrats in most cases head teachers who feel insecure to retain their posts because of changes and has got weak personalities will resort to such strategies to instill fear and manage conflicts in their schools. This method is common by task oriented leaders. The head teachers who cares less about the team work, only focuses on getting the job done and spare very little thought for the well-being of their team. It results to demonization of team work and low retentions of the staff.

13.6 Accommodation

Abdul (2013) affirms that the accommodating strategy is low assertiveness & and high co-operation advocated for when it is necessary to create good will or keep harmony and unity. Only apply when the conflict or outcome is of low magnitude and significance to the head teachers. That means head teacher can't accommodate any conflict between them and their deputies if the outcome of more importance to them. It relies on the judgment of the head teacher but not the deputy so both the parties under the conflict are not given a fair treatment this finally leads to no team work at school setting.

13.7 Compromise

In the view of Abdul, (2013) the moment the conflict involves the same individuals worth the same power and shows the same dedication to the solution to the conflicts then compromising strategy should be used. The question is where on earth will a head teacher accept that they are in the same rank with the deputy head teacher? Never on earth, thus strategy if used may embrace team work through will rarely be used to solve conflict in our public primary schools because of superiority complex.

14. Critical analysis of the stakeholders Perceptions on head teachers and deputy head teachers' conflict development and their impact on team work in public primary schools in Kenya

14.1 Role Ambiguity

Most stakeholders view the role of deputy head teachers as ambiguous for not all the duties are specified. The teacher's service act 1968 that appoints both the head teacher and the deputy head teacher allows the head teacher to assign any other duty to their deputies. What is any other duty? Failure to carry out duty delegated to you by your immediate supervisor is a punishable offence. It leads to interdiction and determination from service. Cooper et al, (2001), Coley and Woodseley (ibid.) and Kyriacou (2001:2a) study emphasized that role ambiguity was part of challenges faced by deputy head teachers. The finding of the study found that deputy head teachers carry out duties that were not well spelt out and because of ambiguity, this leads to role conflict between them and their head teachers. The study found out that intra-role conflict was because of several conflicting of the deputies' position and listed cases where head teachers asked their deputies to perform some conflicting tasks and expected excellent outcome in both cases. Most stake holders holds the vocals that the ambiguity task of the deputies put them at high risk to develop conflict with their deputies because they cannot tell if they are counselors, social workers managers, examiners, secretaries or head teachers personal assistants. Muthenge, (2007) holds the same view that conflict

between head teacher and deputy head teachers persists because deputy head teacher's duties and responsibilities were not well clearly defined leading to confusion and sometimes misuse of the office by their head teachers. The stakeholders therefore, hold the view that this ambiguity that leads to role conflict is a threat to team work in public primary schools.

14.2 Inadequacy of Administrative Authority

Most of stake holders perceived the office of deputy head teachers to be of no influential as the office of the head of departments. This is unlike the head teachers when find their offices more satisfying than when they were deputies Robbins, (2011). Found out that this frustrates and embarrassing. Most deputies are disappointed because they lack leadership influence unlike the lead of departments and the head teachers because of this deputies do not feel to embrace team work where their head teachers are involved as the chairperson and the head of department are recognized while their effort are undermined. This is a threat to team work in public primary schools

14.3 Workload

The stakeholders' perception on the workload of the deputy head teacher in public primary schools is that these teachers are overloaded; the fact strong enough to bring conflict between them and their head teachers, teachers and students and the community at large. With the introduction of free primary education in Kenya, the role the deputy head teacher may handle as class teachers, subject teachers and store keeper may deny them enhance to carry out the contradicting tasks dedicated to them by their head teachers who may need such task done in time. Sheridam (1995) supported this idea and argued that the responsibility of the deputy head teachers had increased such that they had no time or less minimal time for professional development. Unlike the head, teachers who will be privileged to have their workload reduced and long hour to make phone calls and enough hours to advance in their professional developments these results to conflict in the school setting and cannot facilitate team work in the school set up.

14.4 Government Policies

The deputy head teachers are in charge of discipline in learning institution. Since 2001 with the abolishment of canning in schools there has been increase of indiscipline in all schools in the nation. The government failed to give the remedy to their solution hence left the head teachers to find the remedy. The indiscipline is an issue that majority bring conflict between the head teachers and their deputy head teachers the stakeholders feels the government should bring solutions through the head teachers to manage discipline. The stake holders point fingers at the policy makers who don't consider the

consequences of their actions until it is late. When the head teachers blame their deputy head teacher for not maintaining discipline in the school and the parents are blaming the head teachers for the indiscipline, then there can't be team work.

14.5 Working Relationship

The stake holders perceived in most cases that working relationship between deputy head teachers and head teachers are always poor due to constant conflicts, Jaye (2002:3). Found out that there was mistrust between chief administrators of the school and constant conflicts. It was also found out that in most cases whenever deputy could give directive and orders, due to their poor relationship the head teachers could always undo the decisions made by their assistants. Dahlia (2008), study findings found out that most head teachers whenever they could supervise their deputies could lack objectivity and majorised on fault finding. The stake holders has perceptions that most head teachers do not hold regards to their deputies and this always results to poor working relation that affect team work in the school. According to Wathituni (2010) most deputy head teachers are dissatisfied with their head teachers and do not enjoy healthy relationship with their bosses. They consider their head teacher as under miner who can sideline with parents, students and committee members to water down their effort whenever they feel insecure. The stake holder also has the perception that the relationship between the deputy head teacher and the community in most cases is unhealthy since they are the discipline master in their respective schools. In most cases is unhealthy since they are the discipline master in their respective schools. In most cases this has worsen when the relationship between the deputy head teacher is poor because of unresolved conflicts. Hohepa and Lloyd (2009) recited that in most communities deputies are not faces hostility by pupils who are seen as a barrier to the community quest exploit the existing school resources given support and appreciation from parents and the community as in the case of the school head teachers In most cases it is a strategic planned mission by the school leadership In most cases it is strategic planned mission by the school leadership but not by confidence .According gold ring and Housman (1997;29) they argued that poor relationship with members of society is as a result of poor leadership style on the part of the deputy head teacher and head teacher themselves. In according to burns [1978] a leader should be a transformational leader .One who motivates its team to be effective and efficient. A leader should look for ideas that move an organization to reach the institutional goals. It is worth that being a good leader is balancing act.

Jim Rohm once said, *'Being a good leader is balancing act. Your leadership strategy should never rely on just one type of management. It might at first feel like walking a tight rope. But soon balancing multiple leadership attributes will become second nature and allow you to lead multiple dimensions. The challenges of leadership is to be strong, but not rude, not bully, be*

thoughtful but not lazy, be humble but not timid, be proud but not arrogant, have humor but without folly. Ray kroc quoted "No one of us is important than the rest of us". Therefore team work is great to get things done, if you want to go fur go, alone. If you want to go further your walk, with others.'

15. Recommendation

The following recommendations were made from the aforementioned findings;

1. The school heads and deputy head teachers should be fined on conflict preventions ,managements and resolution skills in order to be able to identify signs and symptoms of conflict before they emanate prevent them ,manage them should they exist and resolve them amicably without necessarily destroying team work in their place of work in primary schools in Kenya.
2. Controversial matters and dispute management should be introduced as a learning subject in teachers training collages, undergraduate levels and post graduate levels for all the students persuading education causes in order to bring up teachers who are conversant with conflict resolution and how to handle and deal with controversial issues in public primary schools in Kenya.
3. The ministry of education collaboration with teachers service commission [the teachers' employers] should establish the committee of conflict resolutions at different levels starting school level to national level. the committee should be fully founded to run effectively have enough manpower staffed with experienced ,qualified ,matured personnel in order to solve the conflicts at school levels without affecting team work at our work places in public primary schools in Kenya

16. Conclusions

Education is the key to success. Every little Kenyan deserves better education for a better future. Don't lose to find fault in others life to offer remedy heavy food. From findings of the slowly it was evident that conflict between head teachers and deputy head teachers has adverse effect on team work in public primary schools. It has been found that the major causes of this conflicts are the heads and deputy head teachers leadership styles; the experience and qualifications of the indiscipline or an ethical behaviors superiority complex, management of funds and resources, personality differences favoritism, nepotism, embolism and insecure leadership. It was also founded that these conflicts do not promote team work in most cases among the resolution measures are limited interaction, physical separation confrontation [integration, collaboration] obliging style, dominating style, commendation and

compromisation. In all finding either party the deputy or the head teacher would not be happy with the mechanism that might be applied to solve their conflict. The stakeholders has got reception that deputies has got ambiguous role to play leading to role conflict, over loaded by large work load and added responsibilities that do not value to them. The stake holders also have perceptions that the relationship between most deputies and head teachers at working places is very poor and that kills morals to work as a team. Many findings agreed that conflict is an inevitable outcome in human interaction and according to draw comedic '*No man will make a great leader who wants to do credit for doing or get all the credit for doing it.*'

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